

IPBES AR BBA Chapter 2 – Snowball literature search for literature on business dependency on biodiversity (R5)

Main unit types to measure dependencies.

Sector	Ecosystem service	Dependency measurement	Units
Agriculture	Pollination services	Economic	USD
		Economic	Euros for 2009 for spring
		Economic	Net revenues (\$/ha)
		Economic	USD/ha
		Economic	GBP (£ value - 1996)
		Economic	GBP (£ value - 1996)
		Economic	% EVIP EU
		Economic	USD (2009)
		Economic	USD (2005)
		Economic	Billions USD (2012)
		Economic	income per hectare of coffee production (US\$, 2019)
		Economic	billions of US\$.
		Economic	US\$/ha
		Economic	EUR/Ha
		Productivity	% fruit set at the time of harvesting
Productivity	Annual average of number of honeybee colonies stock density		

Sector	Ecosystem service	Dependency measurement	Units
		Productivity	Mean number of seeds per flower edge of the crop
		Productivity	% fruit set
		Productivity	Average seeds per pod
		Productivity	% pollinator reliance
		Productivity	% fruit set per flower visit number
		Productivity	pollinator dependency ratios
		Productivity	% Fruit set
		Productivity	% yield improvement in coffee with insect pollinator visitation (measured by formed fruits in flowers), as compared with coffee with no visitation.
		Productivity	mean dependence coefficient
		Productivity	coffee yield per hectare of coffee production (kg/ha)
		Productivity	Fruit set ratio calculated as the ratio between the initial number of floral buds in the respective branch and the number of developing fruits
		Quality	Mean total seed weight per pod in spring (g)
		Quality	Berry weight (g)

Sector	Ecosystem service	Dependency measurement	Units
		Quality	apple size, seed number and percent fruit set
		Quality	grams (fruit weight)
		Quality	grams; proportion; CV
		Risk	Average net revenue of coffee (\$/ha) when there is deforestation
		Risk	Marginal rate of pollination substitution due to varroa mite
		Risk	% Vulnerability
		Risk	US\$ (billions) lose due to pollination absence
		Risk	% changed yield compared to baseline
	Water services	Productivity	m ³ /ton
		Productivity	Litres
		Productivity	VWC (kg water/ kg crop)
		Productivity	Virtual water flow - net import (Mm ³)
		Risk	Litres (Stress-weighted water footprint)
		Risk	Virtual water flow - export (Mm ³)
Tourism	Habitat creation and maintenance	Economic	USD